

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

G.AI.A: An Integrated Machine-Learning Platform for Predicting Bioaccumulation and Ecotoxicity of Pharmaceuticals

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Supporting data files

dataset_bcf.csv: The logBCF dataset used in this study.

dataset_lc50.csv: The LC₅₀ dataset used in this study

Methods

Data generation and description. The BCF of various organic chemicals tested on fish species were collected from multiple sources, including publicly available databases and literature reviews. A dataset comprising logBCF values for 1,052 compounds was sourced from Lunghini et al.¹ This dataset included a diverse range of chemicals with environmental and toxicological significance, with logBCF values spanning from -3.30 to 6.78 log units. In addition, experimental BCF data for 352 compounds were collected from Miller et al.,² which compiled their dataset using compounds from the European Chemical Industry Council Long-range Research Initiative (Cefic LRI) project EC07, in collaboration with the European Academy of Standardization e.V. (EURAS). This initiative established the BCF gold standard database across multiple fish species, which is freely accessible at <http://ambit.sourceforge.net/euras/>. Additionally, the ECOTOX database, provided by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), was downloaded as an ASCII file from <https://cfpub.epa.gov/ecotox/>.³ Finally, one of the most carefully selected high quality databases, which is suitable for regulatory purposes, is the database reported from Yuan et al.⁴ This dataset has been utilized to develop both linear and nonlinear models for predicting fish bioconcentration factors and includes 107 compounds with logBCF values ranging from -1.92 to 4.01 log units. The availability and consistency of the underlying experimental metadata are limited, and substantial heterogeneity exists across key parameters such as steady-state confirmation, water concentration type (nominal vs. measured), exposure system, tissue type, and lipid normalization.

More specifically, the Lunghini dataset is itself a compilation of nine major sources, including NITE, CEFIC LRI, DSL, ECOTOX (via OECD Toolbox), ECHA, Arnot & Gobas, Dimitrov, and Fu. These sources vary widely in their reporting standards and completeness, resulting in considerable variability across the underlying BCF experimental conditions. In addition, most entries correspond to steady-state BCF values, particularly those from standardized regulatory tests

(e.g., MITI/NITE, OECD TG 305, EPA OPPTS). A smaller fraction includes kinetic BCFs or BIOFAC-derived values. Because metadata are inconsistently reported, it was not possible to reliably identify or harmonize these categories across all entries. Water concentration (nominal vs. measured) is not explicitly documented within the integrated sources or the relevant scientific publications of the datasets. Consequently, we could not standardize water concentration type, and all BCF values were retained as reported. Tissue information varies widely across the underlying datasets, ranging from whole body to liver, muscle, blood, gill, eggs, lipid/fat, and more. Many entries lack tissue information entirely. Likewise, whether concentrations were lipid-normalized, wet weight, or dry weight was rarely specified. Due to this heterogeneity and frequent lack of metadata, further harmonization was not feasible. Exposure systems include flow-through, semi-static, static, and natural waters, but this information is missing for many entries.

The Miller dataset, derived from the CEFIC LRI project, contains filtered BCF values specific to *Cyprinus carpio*. Reported values correspond to whole-body BCFs, but no additional experimental metadata (steady state, water concentration type, tissue details, exposure system) are available. Given this variability, we retained the Lunghini BCF values as originally reported and explicitly acknowledge in the manuscript that such methodological differences represent systemic sources of uncertainty in large compiled BCF datasets. The curated ECOTOX dataset provides no additional metadata on experimental design, tissue basis, or concentration measurement. The only methodological detail reported is that the BCF values were standardized using lipid fraction data following Li et al. (2011). Yuan reports BCF values generated using bluegill (*Lepomis macrochirus*) following the standardized U.S. EPA (1996) protocol. The dataset also incorporates part of the Jackson database, in which whole-fish BCF values were measured for bluegill. No additional information on water concentration type, steady-state confirmation, or tissue-specific concentrations is available.

Because these databases integrate data from numerous underlying studies, the available metadata are inherently incomplete and heterogeneous. To avoid introducing additional assumptions through recalculation or re-normalization, we retained all reported BCF values exactly as provided by the original sources. Importantly, the underlying studies typically report adherence to standardized testing protocols appropriate for the organisms used, and the compiled datasets themselves (Lunghini, Miller, ECOTOX/EnviroTox, OPERA, and Yuan) are widely used within

the machine-learning and environmental toxicology communities. For these reasons, we consider the use of reported values without further modification to be the most transparent and scientifically defensible approach.

The combined dataset comprises experimental logBCF data for 1,268 unique chemicals related to various fish species. The BCF data were categorized into four datasets of chemical compounds, corresponding to their bioconcentration in the following fish: *Cyprinus*, *Oncorhynchus*, nine other fish species, and all fish species combined.

Since the experimental data were not evenly distributed across the compounds, the median of the median logBCF values for each chemical was calculated to classify the respective compounds based on the REACH regulatory logBCF > 3.30 log units cutoff.⁵ Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System (SMILES) strings were generated for each chemical using Open Babel v 2.4.1.⁶ The following standardization tools to filter out redundant data have been applied: removal of duplicates, exclusion of inorganic chemicals (metals or metal salts), calculation of the molecular weight (MW) of the compounds using the Open Babel chemical toolbox to remove molecules with MW less than 150 Dalton, and generation of the three-dimensional (3D) structures of the molecules to filter out compounds with ambiguous 3D structures. When multiple BCF values were available for the same chemical, we calculated the median of the values for this compound for each Test organism and then we used the median of the medians for each different type of fish. Using the median of the median values, two classes were generated by discretizing the logBCF values based on the REACH regulatory lower cutoff of 3.30 log units.

For the external validation BCF dataset used in the benchmarking study, we relied on experimental BCF data from KOWall3 dataset provided by Xiao et al.⁷ The dataset contains compiled bioaccumulation parameters for 1,724 compounds from multiple databases and literature sources, including ECOTOX⁸, NITE⁹, QSAR Toolbox¹⁰, ECHA¹¹, OPEn structure–activity/property Relationship App (OPERA)¹², CEFIC LRI¹³, DSL and the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard¹⁴.

Additionally, ecotoxicity data, including LC₅₀ values measured up to 96 hours for various organic compounds across different aquatic species and endpoints, were gathered from the EnviroTox¹⁵ and OPERA¹⁶ databases. By merging these datasets, a collection of 4,104 compounds was compiled. Each compound was classified based on the experimentally observed minimum 96-hour LC₅₀ value, using the CLP ruleset threshold (LC₅₀ = 1 mg/L). Similar to the BCF data, the acute

toxicity (LC₅₀) values used in this study were obtained from large compiled datasets that aggregate results from numerous original studies. As a consequence, key experimental details and reporting format are often incomplete or heterogeneous. Below we summarize the level of methodological information available from each source. EnviroTox is a curated extension of EPA ECOTOX and draws directly from the original literature. However, both resources provide limited methodological metadata beyond the toxicity endpoints themselves. Information on control types, water-quality conditions, and exposure verification is typically not included in the aggregated database. EnviroTox explicitly notes that its entries contain a mixture of nominal and measured concentrations, depending on what each underlying study reported. Because the database does not consistently flag which type was used, harmonization or reclassification of LC₅₀ values was not possible. The OPERA toxicity dataset compiles LC₅₀ values from published studies but does not include information on experimental controls, exposure verification (nominal vs. measured), or other test conditions. Only the endpoint values are provided. Within OPERA, measurement units were standardized to log₁₀(mg/L) where feasible, while entries lacking sufficient information were omitted. Exposure routes (static, renewal, flow-through) were retained when reported, but a substantial fraction of entries lacked this information and were classified as “unreported.” Across both datasets, detailed experimental metadata are generally not retained in the compiled sources. Because this information is often missing or inconsistent, further standardization or stratification of LC₅₀ values was not feasible. In the revised manuscript, we clearly acknowledge this limitation and emphasize that variability in exposure verification and control conditions represents an inherent source of uncertainty in large compiled toxicity datasets. Nonetheless, these databases remain among the most widely used, curated, and trusted sources in the ecotoxicology and machine-learning communities, justifying their use in our study.

For the external validation LC₅₀ dataset used in the benchmarking study, we utilized the ADORE benchmark database on acute mortality, retaining only toxicity tests conducted on fish species. The core of ADORE originates from the ECOTOX database, which was harmonized and pre-filtered to include only entries suitable for modeling acute toxicity in fish, crustaceans, and algae. This dataset was further expanded with taxonomic and chemical information from multiple sources and then filtered to retain only acute mortality entries with complete data from all sources. The final dataset primarily consists of organic chemicals. In total, the ADORE dataset contains 33,448

entries, with over 75% (26,114 entries) specifically related to fish species.¹⁷ For the benchmarking study, we utilized the t_F2F dataset, which includes 1,118 compounds with LC₅₀ data across multiple fish species (614 classified as non-ecotoxic and 504 as ecotoxic). Additionally, we used the s-F2F-2 dataset, which contains LC₅₀ data (497 compounds) specifically for the species *Pimephales promelas*, comprising 348 non-ecotoxic and 149 ecotoxic compounds.

Regarding variability across measurements for the same chemical from multiple experiments, in the LC₅₀ dataset the maximum variability observed was 2,099,997 mg/L for the compound with CASRN 27027-29-9 between the species *Tinca tinca* and *Heteropneustes fossilis*. The minimum variability was 0, observed for compounds tested multiple times within the same species, for example, CASRN 100-64-1 in *Pimephales promelas*.

For the logBCF dataset, the maximum variability was 6.29 log units for CASRN 35065-27-1 between *Poecilia reticulata* and *Cyprinus carpio*. Similarly, the minimum variability of 0 was observed for compounds tested multiple times in the same species, such as CASRN 10315-98-7 in *Cyprinus carpio*.

Finally, we thoroughly examined the data availability for all three tools and incorporated external datasets wherever possible. For the VEGA BCF (CAESAR) model¹⁸ although detailed information on the underlying dataset is provided (511 compounds, with measured logBCF values from Dimitrov et al.¹⁹), the actual dataset of 473 organic compounds is not publicly downloadable. Our dataset already incorporates the Dimitrov et al. values through the inclusion of Lunghini et al. data; however, for benchmarking we additionally reconstructed and tested the dataset described in the CAESAR workflow. For the OPERA BCF model, we were able to obtain the full dataset from Mansouri et al.¹² We used their publicly available test set of 157 compounds for external benchmarking of our model. For the T.E.S.T. BCF model²⁰, the final curated dataset is not publicly accessible. The model description indicates that the underlying data were drawn from several sources (Dimitrov et al., Arnot and Gobas²¹, EURAS, Zhao et al.²²). Most of these databases are already represented within our compiled dataset, ensuring substantial overlap, but due to the unavailability of the exact final dataset, direct benchmarking could not be performed. Regarding LC₅₀ models, the VEGA COMBASE LC₅₀ model²³ cites the use of biocides listed by ECHA with toxicity information aggregated from multiple sources. Because the final dataset is not publicly

available, we were unable to benchmark against this model. However, for VEGA's Fathead Minnow LC50 model²⁴, which we used for *Pimephales promelas* validation, the underlying dataset from Su et al.²⁵ was accessible, and we used this dataset directly for benchmarking. Finally, for the T.E.S.T. LC50 model²⁰, the dataset was produced through multi-stage filtering of the ECOTOX database, which also serves as the basis for our external validation dataset (ADORE dataset). As the final curated dataset used by T.E.S.T. is not available, and given the overlap with ECOTOX already represented in our validation workflow, additional benchmarking was not feasible.

Feature selection and models construction. Three types of molecular encodings were tested for training and evaluation of the subsequent ML models. One dimensional (1D), two dimensional (2D), and 3D molecular descriptors were calculated using the PaDEL²⁶ software (version 0.1.16) based on canonical SMILES. In addition, Molecular ACCess System keys (MACCS²⁷), and Morgan²⁸ fingerprints were generated by the RDKit package.²⁹ For the Morgan fingerprints, we generated fingerprints with radii of two, three, and four, each having 1024- and 2048-bit length. Then, the datasets were pre-processed to remove any zero variance or erroneous descriptors and fingerprints. For this purpose, a data handling approach was employed to address the presence of erroneous (NaN) values in the dataset, highly correlated features (correlation coefficient > 0.80) and features with low variance ($\sigma < 0.1$). The StandardScaler function of the Scikit-learn library was employed to normalize each input variable separately based on its mean value and standard deviation. For the MACCS and Morgan fingerprints, scaling was omitted as they have binary values. The normalization process was applied to each training set. Each test set was then normalized using the normalization metrics derived from the respective training set.

Five classifiers (RandomForestClassifier³⁰, XGBClassifier³¹, ExtraTreesClassifier³², AdaBoostClassifier³³, GradientBoostingClassifier³⁴) were used for the classification of chemicals as non-bioaccumulative/non-ecotoxic (class 0) or bioaccumulative/ecotoxic (class 1). RandomForest Classifier and ExtraTrees Classifier follow similar approaches by training multiple decision trees and making final predictions through bagging. XGBClassifier, AdaBoostClassifier and GradientBoostingClassifier utilize boosting techniques that emphasize the training of misclassified data points. Initially, the down-selection of input features concerning the PaDEL descriptors, MACCS and Morgan fingerprints was evaluated by training all the classifiers for 200 epochs on a randomly scaled 70% subset of the input dataset at each epoch. At each epoch, the 20

most important features were identified based on the feature selection algorithm of each classifier. These were extracted for each set of descriptors and fingerprints across all five classifiers. The 20 most frequently selected features for each descriptor and fingerprint set were then retained for further analysis. Next, starting with 5 features and incrementally adding one feature at a time up to 20, the optimal feature set for each algorithm was determined. This was achieved by comparing the mean ROC AUC scores obtained from internal repeated cross-validation (evaluating training set performance) and the mean ROC AUC from model evaluation on 10 external test sets (assessing external validation performance). This systematic approach ensured the selection of the most effective model, optimizing both efficiency and predictive accuracy across the dataset.

Evaluation of model performance. The final dataset was split into a 70% training set and a 30% test set using the `train_test_split` function from the scikit-learn library. Oversampling techniques were applied to each training set, so as to achieve balanced training datasets and augmentation of original training data. The function `SMOTE`³⁵ of `imblearn.over_sampling` library was used to balance the given datasets. In the training datasets of *Cyprinus*, *Oncorhynchus* and nine other fish species, the function `resample` of the Scikit-learn library was also utilized to increase data points maintaining the class distribution. Adding Gaussian noise³⁶ to synthetic data points, generated by `resample`, is also essential in order to increase the robustness of final model.³⁷ The augmentation of data benefits model performance, especially when dealing with small datasets.³⁸ Finally, for the MACCS and Morgan fingerprints, the `SMOTENC` function was used as the oversampling technique for the binary features instead of `SMOTE`. This was because `SMOTENC` can handle categorical features, while `SMOTE` does not guarantee that its output values will be categorical and may produce float-type values (decimals), which is not suitable for binary features.

To enhance model robustness and mitigate overfitting, the training set was further divided into seven folds for 7-fold cross-validation, repeated 50 times with random fold assignments in each repetition. This process was conducted using the `RepeatedStratifiedKFold` function in scikit-learn. During each repetition, six of the seven folds were used for model training, while the remaining fold served as an internal validation set. This ensured consistent performance across different data splits, improving the model's reliability. Once trained on the full training set, each model was evaluated on a completely independent test set, which was not used during training or cross-validation. This independent validation provided an objective assessment of the model's predictive performance in real-world scenarios, preventing performance inflation due to training data

exposure. For performance evaluation, several key statistical metrics were calculated, including accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity³⁹. Additionally, receiver-operating characteristic (ROC) curves were generated, and the corresponding area under the ROC curve (AUC) values were computed to further evaluate model performance. To ensure statistical significance, this evaluation process was repeated over 10 epochs, and the final reported metric values reflect the mean and standard deviation across these repetitions.

To improve the interpretability of our models, we employed the SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) method⁴⁰, which assigns each feature an importance value based on its contribution to the model's predictions. SHAP values provide a quantitative measure of each feature's impact on individual predictions, enabling a clearer understanding of which molecular features most significantly influence bioconcentration and ecotoxicity potential. For each prediction, SHAP values are calculated by iteratively analyzing the effect of adding each feature to the model. This process simulates a cooperative game, where each feature acts as a "player" contributing to the final prediction "score". Using game theory principles, SHAP ensures a fair distribution of each feature's contribution while accounting for interactions between features⁴¹. We established a SHAP value threshold of 0.1, meaning features with SHAP values greater than 0.1 are considered to have a significant impact on model predictions, whereas features with lower values are deemed less influential. SHAP facilitates the visualization and explanation of the model's data impact by highlighting the relative importance of each feature in driving predictions.

For interpretability of our models, the SHAP analysis results from the PaDEL-descriptors model were integrated with insights from the 2D Principal Components Analysis (PCA)⁴² plot, generated from the relevant scaled dataset. The coefficient of each training feature in the first two principal components indicates its positive or negative influence on the respective axis of the plot. This plot captures the majority of variance among the analyzed compounds based on bioconcentration or acute ecotoxicity, effectively defining a chemical space shaped by the training features. SHAP analysis was used to identify key features whose coefficients contribute significantly to the separation of the class 1 cluster in the plot. Moreover, the selected features were further analyzed by examining their value distribution across the two classes. Boxplot distributions were generated using the original descriptor values from the PaDEL descriptor calculations. The confidence intervals of these features in compounds classified as class 1 and class 0 were used to identify

trends in bioaccumulative or ecotoxic compounds based on these descriptors. Finally, the Mann-Whitney U test was applied as a post-processing step to rank the selected features. Mann-Whitney U test⁴³ is a non-parametric method used to test whether two independent samples of observations are drawn from the same or identical distribution.

For the MACCS- and Morgan-based ML models, we calculated the percentage of compounds per class that exhibited a value of 1 for each training feature. SHAP analysis was then applied to determine the influence of class 1 prevalent structural bits on overall model decision-making. The identified substructures can be interpreted as chemical groups associated with bioconcentration and ecotoxicity, providing insights for environmental risk assessment in drug design.

Our curated logBCF and external validation logBCF datasets, along with our LC₅₀ and external validation LC₅₀ datasets, served as benchmarks for assessing our best predicted BCF model against the freely available tools Virtual models for property Evaluation of chemicals within a Global Architecture (VEGA), Open (Quantitative) Structure–Activity/Property Relationship App (OPERA), and Toxicity Estimation Software Tool (T.E.S.T). Similarly, our best predicted LC₅₀ model was evaluated against VEGA and TEST. For BCF prediction, we focused on three well-established VEGA models: 1. VEGA CAESAR, which integrates two sub-models based on theoretical molecular descriptors 2. VEGA Meylan, a KOW-based model incorporating correction factors based on molecular fragments and 3. VEGA Read-Across, which employs a similarity-based approach. Among these, the CAESAR BCF model demonstrated the highest accuracy, albeit by a small margin, and is referred to as “VEGA” throughout the manuscript. Regarding LC₅₀ prediction, the optimal models were IRFMN-Combase, estimating acute toxicity in fish, and KNN-IRFMN, specifically for Fathead Minnow (*Pimephales promelas*). Additionally, we utilized T.E.S.T. 5.1.2 as stand-alone software, applying the Consensus method, which has demonstrated the highest prediction accuracy on external datasets. For this, we selected the endpoints Bioconcentration Factor (BCF) and Fathead Minnow LC₅₀ (96h). Finally, we employed OPERA (version 2.9) from the U.S. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS), an open-source suite of QSAR models designed to predict pharmacokinetic properties, environmental fate parameters, and toxicity endpoints. The BCF predictions were generated using OPERA’s default settings as detailed on its GitHub page (<https://github.com/kmansouri/OPERA>).

Prediction of drugs' metabolites. A comprehensive literature review was conducted to explore publicly available software for *in silico* prediction of drug metabolites in the human body. This review identified eight software and online tools: Metapredictor⁴⁴, CyProduct⁴⁵, Biotransformer 3.0⁴⁶, SyGMA⁴⁷, Chemical Transformation Simulator 1.3.2.2⁴⁸, Metatrans⁴⁹, IMPACTS⁵⁰, and Deep Learning-Based Drug Metabolite Prediction⁵¹. Since our study aimed to infer metabolite structures from parent compounds for subsequent toxicity evaluation, we excluded methodologies primarily designed to identify the specific atomic sites modified by metabolic transformations, known as sites of metabolism (SoM). As a result, we did not include the software CyProduct, Chemical Transformation Simulator 1.3.2.2, IMPACTS, and Deep Learning-Based Drug Metabolite Prediction. Instead, we focused on software that employ machine learning or rule-based approaches and predict the chemical structures of human metabolic products. Among these tools, only four provided open-access code: SyGMA, which uses a rule-based approach to predict CYP450 metabolites by applying metabolization reactions over a specified number of subsequent reaction steps and assigns probabilities to metabolites based on the rule used for their formation, or the product of probabilities in the case of multistep metabolites. Biotransformer 3.0 integrates rule-based methods with machine learning algorithms to predict metabolization products of all documented human metabolic reactions; however, it does not provide scoring for predicted structures. Metatrans uses a deep learning, transformer-based algorithm to predict metabolites of small molecules in humans, though it is limited to predicting one-step metabolic reactions. Last, Metapredictor employs a ML approach using a two-stage framework, first automatically identifying SoMs, followed by metabolite prediction.

Since our work focuses on metabolic prediction for small molecules, particularly drug-like compounds, we evaluated the accuracy and robustness of each software using a validation set composed of drugs and their experimentally verified metabolites. We obtained a total of 221 drugs with experimentally validated metabolites from the ChEMBL database⁵² and assessed the four software tools by calculating the ratio of experimentally identified metabolites to the total predicted metabolites generated by each tool. For Metatrans, the evaluation was performed with a beam size set to 5, which controls the number of metabolites generated. Beam sizes of ~10 and ~2 were also tested but were excluded in earlier evaluation stages due to producing excessive or insufficient metabolites, respectively. SyGMA was evaluated based on

Phase I metabolism, and while Phase II metabolism was also tested, it did not show significant differences in scores, ratios, or metabolite structures compared to Phase I, leading to its exclusion. Biotransformer 3.0 was excluded due to its tendency to generate an excessive number of metabolites, which rendered the predefined ratio impractical for meaningful interpretation. However, despite its exclusion, we still included enviPath⁵³, an ML-based algorithm integrated into Biotransformer, in our assessment. EnviPath predicts microbial biotransformations of organic environmental contaminants and metabolic products from both abiotic and biotic aquatic processes. The Metapredictor software have been evaluated using a beam size of ~15, allowing for the prediction of up to 16 potential metabolic products per drug, which is the default beam size available in Metapredictor⁴⁴.

Results and Discussion

Model performance on bioaccumulation classification. Tables S1, S2, S3 and S4 present the validation metrics for the datasets corresponding to *Cyprinus*, *Oncorhynchus*, nine other fish species and all fish species, using PaDEL descriptors for compound featurization. The results indicate that the models developed through the described methodology effectively classify chemical compounds according to their bioconcentration potential in specific fish species. Finally, Table S5 summarizes the eight most influential descriptors used in the Gradient Boosting model, providing their descriptor types, Mann-Whitney test P-values, weights in the first two principal components from the PCA analysis, and average SHAP values.

Table S1. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with bioconcentration data from the *Cyprinus* dataset.

Classifier	Accuracy mean (\pm std) %	Specificity mean (\pm std) %	Sensitivity mean (\pm std) %	ROC AUC mean (\pm std) %
Random Forest	93.47 (\pm 0.72)	96.39 (\pm 2.12)	90.55 (\pm 2.21)	97.85 (\pm 0.45)
XGBoost	93.11 (\pm 0.94)	95.08 (\pm 1.80)	91.15 (\pm 1.91)	98.06 (\pm 0.43)
ExtraTrees	93.55 (\pm 0.80)	96.89 (\pm 1.25)	90.22 (\pm 1.26)	97.36 (\pm 0.39)
ADABOOST	92.49 (\pm 1.71)	92.84 (\pm 2.84)	92.13 (\pm 1.71)	96.82 (\pm 0.70)
Gradient Boosting	92.70 (\pm 1.41)	93.17 (\pm 2.20)	92.24 (\pm 0.94)	97.69 (\pm 0.58)

Table S2. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with bioconcentration data from the *Oncorhynchus* dataset.

Classifier	Accuracy mean (\pm std) %	Specificity mean (\pm std) %	Sensitivity mean (\pm std) %	ROC AUC mean (\pm std) %
Random Forest	95.11 (\pm 1.34)	93.45 (\pm 2.35)	96.71 (\pm 2.22)	98.85 (\pm 0.71)
XGBoost	96.46 (\pm 0.86)	95.23 (\pm 1.57)	97.74 (\pm 0.92)	98.83 (\pm 0.56)
ExtraTrees	95.87 (\pm 0.67)	94.05 (\pm 1.33)	97.72 (\pm 0.78)	99.26 (\pm 0.37)
ADABOOST	87.23 (\pm 2.29)	84.44 (\pm 3.14)	90.06 (\pm 1.82)	94.84 (\pm 1.24)
Gradient Boosting	92.12 (\pm 1.98)	89.89 (\pm 3.09)	94.42 (\pm 2.35)	96.02 (\pm 1.36)

Table S3. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with bioconcentration data from the *nine other fish species* dataset.

Classifier	Accuracy mean (\pm std) %	Specificity mean (\pm std) %	Sensitivity mean (\pm std) %	ROC AUC mean (\pm std) %
Random Forest	87.56 (\pm 0.97)	96.83 (\pm 0.82)	78.29 (\pm 1.78)	96.18 (\pm 0.57)
XGBoost	92.23 (\pm 0.91)	96.72 (\pm 0.96)	87.73 (\pm 1.79)	98.34 (\pm 0.32)
ExtraTrees	86.99 (\pm 0.71)	97.32 (\pm 1.06)	76.64 (\pm 1.24)	97.16 (\pm 0.44)
ADABOOST	86.59 (\pm 0.94)	92.56 (\pm 1.43)	80.63 (\pm 1.78)	94.84 (\pm 0.64)
Gradient Boosting	85.35 (\pm 1.04)	92.85 (\pm 1.27)	77.85 (\pm 1.85)	94.25 (\pm 0.83)

Table S4. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with bioconcentration data from all fish species.

Classifier	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	ROC AUC

	mean (\pm std) %			
Random Forest	87.85 (\pm 1.40)	92.21 (\pm 1.28)	64.92 (\pm 6.52)	86.06 (\pm 2.12)
XGBoost	85.56 (\pm 1.28)	90.22 (\pm 1.68)	60.67 (\pm 6.51)	83.83 (\pm 1.68)
ExtraTrees	87.01 (\pm 1.32)	91.50 (\pm 1.32)	63.00 (\pm 5.26)	84.76 (\pm 1.59)
ADABOOST	83.57 (\pm 1.13)	85.73 (\pm 1.37)	72.00 (\pm 3.86)	84.83 (\pm 3.30)
Gradient Boosting	86.43 (\pm 0.92)	88.66 (\pm 1.22)	74.50 (\pm 5.97)	86.95 (\pm 2.69)

Table S5. Descriptors used in generating our best predictive model, along with a brief description of their type, their P-values derived from the Mann-Whitney test, their weights in PC1 and PC2 from the PCA analysis, and their mean SHAP values.

Descriptors	Descriptor type	P-value	Weight in PC1 (36.81% of variance)	Weight in PC2 (19.66% of variance)	SHAP value (mean)
CrippenLogP	Crippen logP	1.54e-25	- 0.007	- 0.002	0.513
TopoPSA	Topological polar surface area	2.72e-40	0.440	- 0.243	0.424
ALogP	ALOGP	7.59e-37	0.105	0.489	0.306
SpMin7_Bhv	Burden modified eigenvalues	2.05e-18	-0.029	-0.018	0.231
MAXDN	Atom type E- state	1.42e-28	0.001	- 0.230	0.228

AATS5p	Autocorrelation	2.53e-22	- 0.393	- 0.424	0.192
gmin	Atom type E-state	5.86e-27	- 0.551	0.582	0.185
minsCl	Atom type electrotopological state	2.84e-20	0.580	0.360	0.051

Table S6 presents the validation metrics obtained after 10 training epochs for the most effective models using Morgan fingerprints (with varying radius and bit size) and MACCS fingerprints as input features. The test sets were randomly selected from a dataset containing bioconcentration data across multiple fish species.

Table S6. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with bioconcentration data from multiple fish species.

Fingerprints (radius, n_bits)	Classifier	Accuracy mean (\pm std) %	Specificity mean (\pm std) %	Sensitivity mean (\pm std) %	ROC AUC mean (\pm std) %
Morgan (2, 1024)	ExtraTrees	74.25 (\pm 2.56)	75.98 (\pm 3.79)	65.00 (\pm 5.87)	74.75 (\pm 2.66)
Morgan (2, 2048)	ExtraTrees	75.85 (\pm 2.47)	78.44 (\pm 3.25)	62.00 (\pm 7.02)	74.23 (\pm 2.95)
Morgan (3, 1024)	ExtraTrees	75.72 (\pm 1.85)	78.26 (\pm 2.48)	62.17 (\pm 6.01)	74.44 (\pm 3.04)
Morgan (3, 2048)	XGBoost	73.10 (\pm 2.06)	74.33 (\pm 2.64)	66.50 (\pm 5.50)	76.92 (\pm 2.77)
Morgan (4, 1024)	ExtraTrees	73.36 (\pm 3.04)	73.52 (\pm 4.26)	72.50 (\pm 6.29)	79.20 (\pm 2.99)
Morgan (4, 2048)	XGBoost	72.52 (\pm 3.39)	73.33 (\pm 3.98)	68.17 (\pm 5.19)	77.52 (\pm 3.95)

MACCS (-, 166)	ExtraTrees	84.28 (\pm 1.31)	86.34 (\pm 1.28)	74.06 (\pm 4.15)	84.37 (\pm 2.59)
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Table S7 shows the external validation metrics used to compare the performance of our G.A.I.A model (Gradient Boosting with PaDEL descriptors for predicting bioconcentration) against other publicly available tools, such as VEGA⁵⁴, OPERA¹², and T.E.S.T⁵⁵ using our logBCF dataset.

Table S7. Validation metrics obtained from testing publicly available online software using our logBCF dataset.

Online Software/Model	Accuracy (%)	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
VEGA	78.20	84.39	20.00	51.13
OPERA	72.53	84.22	17.43	51.46
T.E.S.T	89.12	91.66	70.58	75.23
(our) G.A.I.A MODEL	86.43	88.66	74.50	86.95

Tables S8 and S9 present the external validation metrics comparing the performance of our G.A.I.A model (Gradient Boosting with PaDEL descriptors for bioconcentration prediction) with publicly available tools, including VEGA, OPERA, and T.E.S.T, using the external datasets from VEGA (VEGA BCF CAESAR) and OPERA (OPERA BCF).

Table S8. Validation metrics obtained from testing publicly available online software using the VEGA BCF CAESAR dataset.

Online Software/Model	Accuracy (%)	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
VEGA	91.00	97.92	62.37	80.14
OPERA	91.25	95.12	74.19	84.66
T.E.S.T	91.28	98.67	61.29	79.98
(our) G.A.I.A MODEL	90.29	90.91	88.51	89.71

Table S9. Validation metrics obtained from testing publicly available online software using the OPERA BCF dataset.

Online Software/Model	Accuracy (%)	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
VEGA	87.61	98.85	50.00	74.43

OPERA	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
T.E.S.T	20.28	2.56	100.00	51.28
(our) G.A.I.A MODEL	88.60	95.51	64.00	79.75

SHAP analysis was conducted on the top-performing Morgan-based and MACCS-based ML models to evaluate the top 20 structural features and their impact on differentiating bioaccumulative from non-bioaccumulative compounds (Figure S3). To identify key small molecule chemical features, we analyzed the distribution of each structural feature present in the compounds across both classes for the Morgan-based and MACCS-based ML models (Figure S4). To identify the most relevant structural features for predicting bioaccumulation potential in the top-performing Morgan (Figure S5) and MACCS-based ML model, we selected bits with the highest mean absolute SHAP values that were also at least twice as prevalent in the bioaccumulative class compared to the non-bioaccumulative class (Figure S6). In the best MACCS-based ML model (which demonstrated similar performance to the best descriptor-based model), bit 87, representing halogen-containing fragments, had the second-highest mean SHAP value (Figure S6A) and was present in 70% of the bioaccumulative class, compared to only 30% in the non-bioaccumulative class. Similarly, bit 103, which also indicates the presence of chlorine atoms, had a lower impact on distinguishing bioaccumulative from non-bioaccumulative compounds but was still found in 67% of class 1. These findings align with previous research indicating that the presence of chlorine atoms enhances hydrophobicity⁵⁶ and contributes to the environmental persistence of chemical compounds⁵⁷. Finally, bit 62, which represents polycyclic aromatic fragments, had half the mean SHAP value of bit 87. Although it was present in only 30% of bioaccumulative compounds, it appeared in just 10% of the non-bioaccumulative class, indicating that these fragments are predominantly associated with bioaccumulative compounds. Compounds containing these fragments are often resistant to biodegradation⁵⁸, resulting in prolonged environmental persistence and accumulation within the food chain. Structural features

such as halogen-containing fragments and polycyclic aromatic systems can increase a compound's lipophilicity, facilitating its absorption and retention in the lipid-rich tissues of aquatic organisms. Additionally, these substructures may exhibit specific binding affinities to proteins and enzymes, further prolonging their retention time and enhancing bioaccumulation potential. For example, the presence of multiple chlorine atoms can strengthen interactions with biological macromolecules, potentially inhibiting metabolic pathways responsible for degradation and elimination⁵⁹. These chemical features have also been recognized as key factors in enhancing the bioaccumulation of compounds in other *in silico* models^{60,61}. Recognizing these structural alerts is crucial for regulatory agencies, as they provide a simple yet effective visualization tool for risk assessment and regulatory decision-making.

Model performance on ecotoxicity classification. Table S9 presents the validation metrics for the datasets corresponding to all fish species using PaDEL descriptors for compound featurization. Tables S10 and S11 provide the full list of descriptors and the final subset of eight descriptors, respectively, used in constructing the optimal ecotoxicity prediction model (ExtraTrees classifier). Each table includes a brief description of the descriptor types, their associated P-values from the Mann–Whitney test, loadings on the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) from PCA, and average SHAP values reflecting their contribution to model predictions.

Table S9. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets.

Classifier	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	ROC AUC
	mean (\pm std) %			
Random Forest	86.76 (\pm 1.04)	90.16 (\pm 1.30)	74.98 (\pm 3.73)	90.73 (\pm 1.57)
XGBoost	85.59 (\pm 1.09)	89.70 (\pm 0.95)	71.31 (\pm 3.60)	88.96 (\pm 1.51)
ExtraTrees	87.99 (\pm 1.13)	92.21 (\pm 0.97)	73.38 (\pm 3.16)	90.96 (\pm 1.35)
ADABoost	76.84 (\pm 1.13)	78.13 (\pm 1.88)	72.39 (\pm 4.08)	83.29 (\pm 1.70)
Gradient Boosting	75.36 (\pm 0.68)	77.24 (\pm 1.06)	70.00 (\pm 3.17)	80.53 (\pm 1.28)

Table S10. The full set of descriptors used in generating our best ecotoxic predictive model, along with a brief description of their type, their P-values derived from the Mann-Whitney test, their weights in PC1 and PC2 from the PCA analysis, and their mean SHAP values.

Descriptors	Descriptor type	P-value	Weight in PC1 (36.81% of variance)	Weight in PC2 (19.66% of variance)	SHAP value (mean)
ALogP	ALOGP	2.08e-76	- 0.001	0.686	0.078
AATS5p	Autocorrelation	2.60e-106	0.015	0.103	0.074
SpMax5_Bhm	Burden modified eigenvalues	9.90e-125	0.401	- 0.225	0.069
VP-3	Chi path	1.20e-123	0.167	0.120	0.065
CrippenLogP	Crippen logP	1.30e-136	0.225	0.314	0.064
XLogP	XLogP	1.25e-92	-0.059	0.323	0.064
ZMIC1	Information content	9.80e-124	0.011	-0.128	0.057
ATS3m	Autocorrelation	4.96e-127	0.422	0.074	0.055
SpMax4_Bhm	Burden modified eigenvalues	1.58e-118	-0.424	0.106	0.053
ATS2m	Autocorrelation	1.09e-124	-0.209	0.204	0.048
SpMax1_Bhp	Burden modified eigenvalues	1.92e-79	0.028	-0.112	0.047
ATS4m	Autocorrelation	1.21e-122	0.395	0.107	0.045
ATS1m	Autocorrelation	7.16e-117	0.128	-0.341	0.045
SpMax3_Bhm	Burden modified eigenvalues	3.68e-119	-0.427	-0.188	0.044

Table S11. The eight most important descriptors used in generating our best ecotoxic predictive model, along with a brief description of their type, their P-values derived from the Mann-Whitney test, their weights in PC1 and PC2 from the PCA analysis, and their mean SHAP values.

Descriptors	Descriptor type	P-value	Weight in PC1 (36.81% of variance)	Weight in PC2 (19.66% of variance)	SHAP value (mean)
ALogP	ALOGP	2.08e-76	- 0.001	0.686	0.078
AATS5p	Autocorrelation	2.60e-106	0.015	0.103	0.074
SpMax5_Bhm	Burden modified eigenvalues	9.90e-125	0.401	- 0.225	0.069
VP-3	Chi path	1.20e-123	0.167	0.120	0.065
CrippenLogP	Crippen logP	1.30e-136	0.225	0.314	0.064
ZMIC1	Information content	9.80e-124	0.011	-0.128	0.057
ATS3m	Autocorrelation	4.96e-127	0.422	0.074	0.055
SpMax1_Bhp	Burden modified eigenvalues	1.92e-79	0.028	-0.112	0.047

Table S12 presents the validation metrics obtained after 10 training epochs for the most effective models using Morgan fingerprints (with varying radius and bit size) and MACCS fingerprints as input features. The test sets were randomly selected from a dataset containing ecotoxicity data across multiple fish species.

Table S12. Cross-model validation metrics after 10 epochs of classification on random test sets. The test sets were derived from a dataset with LC₅₀ data from multiple fish species.

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Fingerprints (radius, n_bits)	Classifier	Accuracy mean (\pm std) %	Specificity mean (\pm std) %	Sensitivity mean (\pm std) %	ROC AUC mean (\pm std) %
Morgan (2, 1024)	Random Forest	75.81 (\pm 1.77)	80.05 (\pm 1.77)	63.50 (\pm 3.04)	76.29 (\pm 1.47)
Morgan (2, 2048)	XGBoost	75.64 (\pm 1.15)	83.42 (\pm 1.95)	53.09 (\pm 2.13)	73.67 (\pm 1.28)
Morgan (3, 1024)	Random Forest	76.36 (\pm 2.38)	78.99 (\pm 3.98)	67.51 (\pm 3.83)	79.31 (\pm 1.10)
Morgan (3, 2048)	XGBoost	75.07 (\pm 2.34)	78.94 (\pm 3.04)	62.09 (\pm 3.99)	76.58 (\pm 2.46)
Morgan (4, 1024)	ExtraTrees	76.98 (\pm 1.07)	81.06 (\pm 1.43)	63.28 (\pm 2.72)	77.21 (\pm 1.77)
Morgan (4, 2048)	Gradient Boosting	74.24 (\pm 1.84)	78.89 (\pm 2.21)	58.64 (\pm 1.33)	74.06 (\pm 2.18)
MACCS (-, 166)	ExtraTrees	75.23 (\pm 1.61)	78.10 (\pm 2.94)	65.59 (\pm 4.10)	80.14 (\pm 1.70)

To identify key small molecule chemical features that contribute ecotoxicity in fish species, SHAP analysis was performed on the top-performing Morgan-based and MACCS-based ML models to assess the top 20 structural features and their influence on distinguishing ecotoxic from non-ecotoxic compounds (Figure S11). The distribution of each structural feature across both classes in both fingerprint-based models are shown in Figure S12. To identify the most relevant structural features for predicting ecotoxicity potential in the top-performing Morgan (Figure S13) and MACCS-based ML model, we selected bits with the highest mean absolute SHAP values that were also at least twice as prevalent in the in the ecotoxic class compared to the non-ecotoxic class (Figure S14). In the best MACCS-based ML model (which outperformed the other fingerprint-based models), bits 145 and 125, which represent the presence of single or fused aromatic rings, ranked first and third in mean SHAP value (Figure S11A), respectively. These features were found in nearly 40% of ecotoxic compounds, compared to less than 20% in the non-ecotoxic class. This aligns with previous studies suggesting that aromatic rings, such as carbonyl-benzene moieties⁶²,

contribute to high aquatic toxicity^{63–65}. Additionally, bit 134, representing the presence of halogen atoms, was the most prevalent in the ecotoxic class (50%) and had the second-highest mean SHAP value. Similarly, bit 87, associated with halogen-containing fragments, also identified as an important feature in our best MACCS-based ML model for bioconcentration, was present in 40% of ecotoxic compounds but only in approximately 20% of non-ecotoxic ones, though it had the lowest mean SHAP value. These findings are consistent with literature indicating that a higher number of halogen groups in chemical structures enhances aquatic toxicity^{66,67}.

Comparison with previous studies for ecotoxicity classification. The ADORE dataset consists of 33,448 entries, with over 75% (26,114 entries) pertaining to fish. The dataset presents three levels of complexity for acute mortality challenges: (1) the most complex level, which includes all three taxonomic groups (fish, crustaceans, and algae), (2) an intermediate level focused on a single taxonomic group, and (3) the least complex level, which is restricted to individual, well-represented test species. In this study, we concentrated on the fish taxonomic group. Additionally, the dataset contains only entries with LC₅₀ as the endpoint for fish mortality, categorized into four fish species: multiple fish species, *Pimephales promelas*, *Lepomis macrochirus*, and *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. The dataset was preprocessed by removing non-96-hour LC₅₀/EC₅₀ values within the non-ecotoxic range (LC₅₀/EC₅₀ >1 mg/L), selecting the minimum LC₅₀/EC₅₀ value per fish, excluding compounds already present in our training LC₅₀ dataset, filtering out compounds with missing values (NaNs) in the training features of our LC₅₀ model, and eliminating compounds with molecular weights below 150 Da. As a result, the final dataset included only previously unseen compounds from our acute ecotoxicity dataset with molecular weights exceeding 150 Da. For benchmarking, we utilized the t_F2F dataset, which comprises 1,118 compounds with LC₅₀ data for multiple fish species, including 614 non-ecotoxic and 504 ecotoxic compounds. A comparison of the chemical space covered by the compounds in the ADORE dataset, which includes data from multiple fish species and our curated LC₅₀ dataset is presented in Figure S15. Additionally, we used the s-F2F-2 dataset, which contains 497 compounds with LC₅₀ data specifically for *Pimephales promelas*, as this species was used to train the T.E.S.T models. The dataset consists of 348 non-ecotoxic and 149 ecotoxic compounds.

Table S13 shows the external validation metrics used to compare the performance of our G.A.I.A model (ExtraTrees with PaDEL descriptors for predicting ecotoxicity) against other publicly available tools, such as VEGA⁵⁴ and T.E.S.T⁵⁵ using our LC50 dataset.

Table S13. Validation metrics obtained from testing publicly available online software using our LC₅₀ dataset.

Online Software/Model	Accuracy (%)	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
VEGA	85.04	88.11	33.33	55.00
T.E.S.T	78.49	80.97	66.40	67.00
(our) G.A.I.A MODEL	87.99	92.21	73.38	90.96

Table S14 shows the external validation metrics used to compare the performance of our G.A.I.A model (ExtraTrees with PaDEL descriptors for predicting ecotoxicity) against other publicly available tools, such as VEGA⁵⁴ and T.E.S.T⁵⁵ using the [VEGA Fathead Minnow LC₅₀](#) dataset.

Table S14. Validation metrics obtained from testing publicly available online software using the LC₅₀ dataset.

Accuracy (%)	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	ROC AUC (%)
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Online Software/Model				
VEGA	88.77	96.83	33.78	65.31
T.E.S.T	93.18	97.41	63.38	80.39
(our) G.A.I.A MODEL	89.46	89.96	87.69	88.82

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SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Comparison of the chemical space covered by compounds in our BCF dataset with (A) KOWall3, (B) VEGA BCF (CAESAR), and (C) OPERA BCF external datasets. Additionally, comparison of the chemical space of our LC50 dataset with (D) ADORE and (E) VEGA Fathead Minnow external datasets.

Figure S2. Distribution of logBCF values in our dataset (BCF_dataset) and the external validation set (KOWall3_dataset), along with three key chemical properties: molecular weight, logS and logP.

Figure S3. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves from 10-epoch validation runs using the Gradient Boosting classifier, the best-performing model for predicting chemical bioconcentration potential.

Figure S4. Mean absolute SHAP values of the top 20 structural features contributing to the prediction of bioconcentration potential in the best-performing ML models based on A) MACCS fingerprints and B) Morgan fingerprints.

A)

B)

Figure S5. Class-wise distribution of the top 20 structural features in the best-performing ML models based on A) MACCS fingerprints and B) Morgan fingerprints for predicting the bioconcentration potential of chemical compounds.

Figure S6. A) Class-wise distribution of the selected structural features in the best-performing Morgan-based machine learning model (Extra Trees model trained with Morgan fingerprints, radius 4, 1024 bits) for predicting the bioconcentration potential of chemical compounds. B) Mean absolute SHAP values for the selected structural features in the best-performing Morgan-based ML model C) The most significant Morgan bits along with their SMARTS representations and 2D chemical depictions.

Figure S7. A) Distribution of the selected structural features across both classes in the best-performing MACCS-based ML model. B) Mean absolute SHAP values for the selected structural features in the best-performing MACCS-based ML model C) The most significant MACCS bits along with their SMARTS representations and 2D chemical depictions.

Figure S8. Comparison of chemical space covered by the compounds in the Xiao et al logBCF dataset of multiple fish species (external_BCF_dataset) and our logBCF dataset (BCF_dataset). Each plot delineates the chemical space as defined by the values of training features used in the Gradient Boosting model. The density values along the y-axis represent the count of compounds per value normalized by the total number of compounds within each dataset. This metric is employed to facilitate a comparative analysis between the two datasets. The x-axis displays the values of each training feature.

Figure S9. Distribution of LC_{50} values in our dataset and the external validation set, along with three key chemical properties: molecular weight, $\log S$ and $\log P$.

Figure S10. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves from 10-epoch validation runs using the ExtraTrees classifier, the best-performing model for predicting chemical ecotoxicity potential.

Figure S11. A) Histogram displaying the mean absolute SHAP values of all features employed in training the ExtraTrees classifier. B) Distribution of local SHAP values for each feature used in the ExtraTrees model.

Figure S12. Mean absolute SHAP values of the top 20 structural features contributing to the prediction of ecotoxicity potential in the best-performing ML models based on A) MACCS fingerprints and B) Morgan fingerprints.

Figure S13. Class-wise distribution of the top 20 structural features in the best-performing ML models based on A) MACCS fingerprints and B) Morgan fingerprints for predicting the ecotoxicity potential of chemical compounds.

Figure S14. A) Class-wise distribution of the selected structural features in the best-performing Morgan-based machine learning model (Random Forest model trained with Morgan fingerprints, radius 3, 1024 bits) for predicting the ecotoxicity potential of chemical compounds. B) Mean absolute SHAP values for the selected structural features in the best-performing Morgan-based ML model C) The most significant Morgan bits along with their SMARTS representations and 2D chemical depictions.

Figure S15. A) Distribution of the selected structural features across both classes in the best-performing MACCS-based ML model. B) Mean absolute SHAP values for the selected structural features in the best-performing MACCS-based ML model C) The most significant MACCS bits along with their SMARTS representations and 2D chemical depictions. Bits 103 and 107 are omitted, as their representative substructures closely resemble bit 134.

Figure S16. Comparison of chemical space covered by the compounds in the ADORE dataset of multiple fish species (t_F2F) and our acute ecotoxicity dataset (Envopera). Each plot delineates the chemical space as defined by the values of training features used in the ExtraTrees model. The density values along the y-axis represent the count of compounds per value normalized by the total number of compounds within each dataset. This metric is employed to facilitate a comparative analysis between the two datasets. The x-axis displays the values of each training feature.

Figure S17. 2D t-SNE plots illustrating the pairwise distances between compound descriptors in the training datasets for A) bioconcentration and B) ecotoxicity. Stars indicate the positions of the input compounds relative to the class 0 and class 1 clusters, offering further insight into their predicted classifications.